

A Single-Center Cross-Sectional Observational Study Determining the Prevalence and Predictors of Stunting in Children with Type-1 DiabetesKhodaija Mahvish¹, Samiksha Sharma², B.K Singh³¹Senior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, NMCH, Patna, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, NMCH, Patna, Bihar, India³Professor and HOD, Department of Pediatrics, NMCH, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 10-07-2023 Revised: 16-08-2023 / Accepted: 22-09-2023

Corresponding author: Dr. Khodaija Mahvish

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Aim:** The aim of the present study was to determine the prevalence and predictors of stunting in children with Type-1 diabetes.**Methods:** This was a single-center, cross-sectional, observational study. Children (1–18 years) with T1D along with their parents who attended the at department of pediatrics for 12 months. during the study period were approached. Parents were provided written informed consent and children gave assent for the study. 250 children were included in the study.**Results:** Of the 250 children studied, 120 (48%) were boys and 130 (52%) were girls. Mean age of the children in the study group was 11.8±3.8 (1.2–18) years and the average duration of diabetes was 5.0±3.7 years. The children's mean HbA1c was 10.0±2.4%. We reported 20% prevalence of stunting in our cohort of children with T1D. Stunted children had higher cholesterol, lower hemoglobin, lower midparental height Z-scores, and higher urinary albumin creatinine ratio. Binary logistic regression revealed that pre-existing comorbidities, compromised renal function, longer disease duration, and short mid-parental height were significant predictors of stunting.**Conclusion:** Our study suggested that a little under one-sixth of children with T1D had short stature. Monitoring growth in these patients, especially in subjects with short parents, prolonged duration of diabetes, existing comorbidities, and deteriorating renal function are critical.**Keyword:** Children, Insulin-like growth factor 1, Midparental height, Stunting, Type-1 diabetes.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

During childhood and adolescence, the longitudinal growth of bones represents one of the most relevant changes of the body composition. [1] Bone growth occurs at different rates and results from complex mechanisms involving a multitude of regulatory hormones. These events are directly influenced by the interaction between genetic and environmental factors. [1-4] Nutritional status represents one of the most relevant factors affecting these interactions. However, several other factors, and especially chronic diseases, might also strongly modulates these complex mechanisms. In fact, chronic diseases, by directly or indirectly modulating bone and hormonal status, may affect growth and final height of subjects with a disease onset during childhood or adolescence. Several lines of evidence have clearly shown that growth is often impaired in children and adolescents with type 1 diabetes (T1D).

Type-1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) is a chronic disorder characterized by a deficiency in insulin production. It is the major form of diabetes diagnosed in children and is commonly referred to as “childhood-onset” diabetes. The worldwide prevalence of T1DM in children under the age of 20 years in 2021 was estimated to be 1.2 million cases (149,500 incident cases), with the highest prevalence in India. [5] Growth has previously been reported to be impaired in children with diabetes. [6-8] The Indian experience with paediatric diabetes is important to learn from, not only because of the high burden of diabetes (likely prevalence 5 million diabetic children and adolescents; of which 3–4 million face poverty along with diabetes) but also because of problems like death before diagnosis (due to missed diagnosis), poor management because of low awareness and high costs, limited availability of insulin and poor cold chains in rural areas, limited availability of blood glucose strips, yet greater

family support, as in many developing countries of Asia and Africa. In developing countries, medical training pays little attention to chronic disorders and long term care, since the focus is mainly on infections and other acute illnesses, vaccinations, reproductive issues, and nutrition. Other major limitations are poor infrastructure and low public expenditure on health, leading to significant out-of-pocket expenses by individuals. [9] Poor care and delayed or no prevention strategies lead to more complications. Due to these inadequacies in the medical care system, the patient and family are trapped in a vicious cycle of increased acute and chronic complications, thus further elevating costs, mortality, absenteeism from work and hence decrease in income, employability, and quality of life, further pushing the family into indebtedness and poverty.

The aim of the present study was to determine the prevalence and predictors of stunting in children with Type-1 diabetes.

Materials and Methods

This was a single-center, cross-sectional, observational study. Children (1–18 years) with T1D along with their parents who attended the department of pediatrics, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India for 12 months. During the study period were approached. Since we wanted to assess the effect of complications and comorbidities on growth failure, all patients who attended the hospital during the study period and who agreed to take part in the study were included in the study. Parents were provided written informed consent and children gave assent for the study. 250 children were included in the study.

Clinical history and examination: Data on the age of patients, age at diagnosis of diabetes, duration of diabetes, current medications, number of admissions for ketoacidosis, birth weight, history of other illness, family history, type of insulin regimen, and total dose of insulin per day were collected using standardized questionnaires by a pediatrician. Medical history provided by parents was verified from hospital medical records. Tanner staging for sexual maturity was performed by a pediatric endocrinologist. Pubertal staging was classified as prepubertal, pubertal, and post-pubertal. [10,11] **Physical activity** was assessed using validated activity questionnaires adapted for Indian children. [12] **Anthropometry:** Standing height of patients and parents was measured using a portable stadiometer (Leicester Height Meter, Child Growth Foundation, and UK) to the nearest millimeter and weight was measured using an electronic scale to the nearest 100 g. Body mass index (BMI) was computed by dividing weight in kilograms by height in meter square. Subsequently,

the height, weight, and BMI were converted to Z scores using Indian references. [13]

Dietary Data

Dietary data were recorded using the 1day dietary recall method on 1 week day and a holiday and a mean were computed. Trained nutritionists interviewed the children along with their primary caregivers to get an accurate estimate of the foods consumed. Nutrient intakes were then computed using the cooked food database software, CDiet. [14] Adequacies of nutrient intakes were estimated by computing the percentage of the recommended dietary allowance (RDA) for Indian children for each nutrient consumed. [15]

Biochemical measurements: Glycemic control was evaluated by measuring glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c). A fasting blood sample (5 ml) was collected between 7 am and 9 am by a pediatric phlebotomist. HbA1c was measured by high-performance liquid chromatography (BIO-RAD, Germany). Hemoglobin was estimated by spectrophotometry at a wavelength of 555 nm using a Horiba Yumizen H500 hematology analyzer. The fasting blood samples were then assessed for lipid profile (total cholesterol, triglycerides, and HDL-C) using the enzymatic method and low-density lipoprotein-cholesterol concentrations were calculated by the Friedewald formula. The first voided urine sample was collected in a sterile container and urine was assessed for urine microalbumin, creatinine, and urine albumin: creatinine ratio (ACR) which were computed using a ratio of urine albumin to urine creatinine (urinary albumin and creatinine concentrations determined using radioimmunoassay and Jaffe's method, respectively). Samples were not taken during menstrual cycles, fever, after heavy exercise, or marked hyperglycemia. If ACR was in the range between 0 and 30 ug/mg, it was considered normal. Single high value of early morning urinary ACR (above 30 ug/mg) was considered as altered ACR. Serum IGF1 concentrations were analyzed by a solid-phase enzyme linked immunosorbent assay with an intraassay coefficient of variation (CV) of 4.7% and interassay CV of 7.2%. The IGF1 concentrations were then converted into Zscores using available reference data. [16]

Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses were carried out using the SPSS for Windows software program, version 26 (SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA). All outcome variables were tested for normality before performing statistical analyses. Differences in means were tested using Student's t-test for parametric data, Mann-Whitney U-test for non-parametric data, and Chi-square test for categorical variables. For testing

relationships between dichotomous dependent variables and continuous predictors, binary logistic regression analysis was carried out. The dependent variable in the model was stunting while the independent variables were midparental height Z-scores, tanner stage (classified into two groups as

pre-pubertal and in puberty/post-pubertal), diabetes duration, glycemic control (HbA1c), and comorbidities/ complications such as hypothyroidism, altered ACR, and lipids. $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Clinical/laboratory findings of patients classified by stature

Parameter	Stunting (n=50)	No stunting (n=200)	p-value
Age (years)	12±3.7	11.7±4	0.022
Diabetes duration (years)	7.3±4	4.6±3.2	0.000
Height Z scores (15.7% stunted)	-2.5±0.7	-0.7±0.8	0.000
Weight Z scores	-1.6±0.7	-0.7±0.8	0.124
BMI Z scores	-0.5±0.8	-0.5±0.7	0.000
Midparental height Z scores	-1.5±0.7	-0.7±0.7	0.000
Physical activity (min/week)	296.4±226.4	302.6±228.2	0.786
PercentRDA energy (%)	69.2±27.4	72.6±31.8	0.346
PercentRDA protein (%)	105.5±54.4	114.6±60.5	0.206
PercentRDA zinc (%)	67.3±52.4	68.2±47.3	0.889
Insulin (unit/kg/day)	1.2±0.4	1.1±0.3	0.162
Creatinine (mmol/L)	0.1±0.0	0.1±0.0	0.044
HbA1c (mmol/L)	13.7±0.8	13.6±0.8	0.314
Vitamin D (ng/ml)	19.4±9.1	18.4±9.1	0.540
Hemoglobin (g/dl)	12.8±1.4	13.7±1.4	0.022
Total cholesterol (mmol/L)	4.4±1.0	3.8±0.9	0.007
LDL cholesterol (mmol/L)	1.0±1.0	1.0±0.8	0.366
Albumin Creatinine ratio (ug/mg)	240.4±645.5	28.2±76.4	0.000

Of the 250 children studied, 120 (48%) were boys and 130 (52%) were girls. Mean age of the children in the study group was 11.8±3.8 (1.2–18) years and the average duration of diabetes was 5.0±3.7 years. The children's mean HbA1c was 10.0±2.4%. We

reported 20% prevalence of stunting in our cohort of children with T1D. Stunted children had higher cholesterol, lower hemoglobin, lower midparental height Z-scores, and higher urinary albumin creatinine ratio.

Table 2: Binary logistic regression to determine the predictors of stunting

Parameter	OR	Wald	Sig	95% CI for EXP (B)	
				Lower	Upper
Duration of diabetes	1.424	20.80	0.000	1.232	1.710
Midparental height Z-scores	3.547	12.316	0.000	1.78	7.314
Tanner stage	0.160	8.188	0.005	0.047	0.560
Children having comorbidities (hypothyroidism, vitiligo, and celiac disease)	4.396	3.542	0.05	0.926	19.409
Albumin: creatinine ratio	5.760	8.232	0.005	1.745	19.028
Cholesterol	0.690	0.276	0.604	0.15	3.234
Vitamin D	0.744	0.445	0.508	0.24	1.867
HbA1c	1.64	0.882	0.342	0.548	4.325
IGF1 zscores	0.702	2.247	0.134	0.443	1.115
Sports duration (weekly/min)	1	0.01	0.924	0.949	1.002
Percent RDA energy	0.997	0.036	0.867	0.96	1.018
Constant	0.004	14.4	0		

While performing logistic regression analysis, we considered children with T1D with or without stunting as the dependent variable while diabetes duration, physical activity and dietary intake (energy percentage of as per recommended daily allowance), midparental height Z-scores, tanner

stage, comorbidities, urinary ACR, serum cholesterol, HbA1c, and IGF-1 Z-scores as the independent variables. Binary logistic regression revealed that children with comorbidities (such as hypothyroidism, vitiligo, and celiac disease), children having compromised renal function,

longer disease duration, children who had achieved puberty, and children with short midparental height were significant predictors of stunting ($p < 0.05$). Variables such as physical activity and dietary intake of energy, cholesterol concentrations, HbA1c, and IGF-1 concentrations were not significant predictors ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion

Type-1 diabetes mellitus (T1D) is one of the most common chronic pediatric endocrine disorders in which the β -cells of the pancreas do not produce enough insulin to maintain normal glucose metabolism. [17] The International Diabetes Federation Atlas 10th edition estimates 1,211,900 children and adolescents younger than 20 years to have T1D globally. T1D age-standardized incidences are highest in populations of North European origin and in several countries in the Middle Eastern and North African Region. India and the United States of America have the highest numbers of estimated incident cases of T1D followed by various other populous countries. [18] T1D and its complications, including impaired childhood growth/short stature, thus remain a major concern. [19] A child with short stature or stunting is a child whose height/length is $< -2SD$ (i.e., below the 2.3 percentile) for his/her age and gender. Stunting (low height-for-age) is considered to be a significant indicator of nutritional assessment of children and adolescents and is also an indicator of chronic under nutrition. [20]

Of the 250 children studied, 120 (48%) were boys and 130 (52%) were girls. Mean age of the children in the study group was 11.8 ± 3.8 (1.2–18) years and the average duration of diabetes was 5.0 ± 3.7 years. The children's mean HbA1c was $10.0 \pm 2.4\%$. We reported 20% prevalence of stunting in our cohort of children with T1D. Stunted children had higher cholesterol, lower hemoglobin, lower midparental height Z-scores, and higher urinary albumin creatinine ratio. While performing logistic regression analysis, we considered children with T1D with or without stunting as the dependent variable while diabetes duration, physical activity and dietary intake (energy percentage of as per recommended daily allowance), midparental height Z-scores, tanner stage, comorbidities, urinary ACR, serum cholesterol, HbA1c, and IGF-1 Z-scores as the independent variables. Binary logistic regression revealed that children with comorbidities (such as hypothyroidism, vitiligo, and celiac disease), children having compromised renal function, longer disease duration, children who had achieved puberty, and children with short midparental height were significant predictors of stunting ($p < 0.05$). Variables such as physical activity and dietary intake of energy, cholesterol concentrations, HbA1c, and IGF-1 concentrations were not significant predictors ($p > 0.05$). The

pubertal peak in HbA1c is likely due not only to physiological changes, such as increased insulin resistance during puberty [21] but also to behavioral resistance to lifestyle change. [22] We also analyzed how individual differences in pubertal height growth relate to child specific physiological characteristics. The course of disease, in particular the age at diagnosis and the time since diagnosis, affected mean height and the timing of the growth spurt—later diagnosis and longer duration were independently associated with greater height and later puberty. However there was an important sex difference: girls were affected more in terms of size, particularly with mean HbA1c, where a 1 SD increase in HbA1c was associated with being 2 cm shorter. Boys were affected more in terms of timing and intensity, which was positively associated with age at diagnosis and the duration of the disease. Thus, broadly speaking, the impact of T1DM was to reduce height in girls, whereas in boys it slowed and delayed growth. The dependence of pubertal growth on growth hormone and testosterone in girls and boys, respectively, may be important for this observed difference as suggested by Dunger et al. [23] A recent study by Blasetti et al [24] also showed that shorter subjects had a higher HbA1c SDS, but they did not report any sex differences.

In our study, we did not find a role of glycemic control in causing stunting in children with T1D. Similar results have been reported in a study conducted in Royal Children's Hospital (RCH), Melbourne, Australia, which concluded no significant association between metabolic control and linear growth of children with T1D. [25] In contrast to our results, a study conducted in Jeddah Kingdom of Saudi Arabia from June to August 2017 showed that there was no association between the duration of diabetes and the height, weight, or BMI Z-scores. Besides, they also report a correlation between HbA1c levels and height Z-scores. This may be explained by exclusion of children with hypothyroidism, celiac disease, and familial short stature. [26,27]

Conclusion

Our study suggested that a little under one-sixth of children with T1D had short stature. Monitoring growth in these patients, especially in subjects with short parents, prolonged duration of diabetes, existing comorbidities, and deteriorating renal function are critical.

References

1. Wit JM, Camacho-Hübner C. Endocrine regulation of longitudinal bone growth. Cartilage and bone development and its disorders. 2011; 21:30-41.

2. Kember NF. Cell kinetics and the control of growth in long bones. *Cell Proliferation*. 1978 Sep;11(5):477-85.
3. Kember NF. Cell kinetics and the control of bone growth. *Acta Paediatrica*. 1993 Dec;82: 61-5.
4. Salmon Jr WD. A hormonally controlled serum factor which stimulates sulfate incorporation by cartilage in vitro. *J Lab Clin Med*. 1957; 49:825-36.
5. Ogle GD, James S, Dabelea D, Pihoker C, Svensson J, Maniam J, Klatman EL, Patterson CC. Global estimates of incidence of type 1 diabetes in children and adolescents: Results from the International Diabetes Federation Atlas. *Diabetes research and clinical practice*. 2022 Jan 1; 183:109083.
6. Brown M, Ahmed ML, Clayton KL, Dunger DB. Growth during childhood and final height in type 1 diabetes. *Diabetic Medicine*. 1994 Mar;11(2):182-7.
7. Boggetti E, Riva MC, Bonfanti R, Meschi F, Viscardi M, Chiumello G. Growth changes in children and adolescents with short-term diabetes. *Diabetes Care*. 1998 Aug 1;21(8):12 26-9.
8. Ahmed ML, Connors MH, Drayer NM, Jones JS, Dunger DB. Pubertal growth in ID DM is determined by HbA1c levels, sex, and bone age. *Diabetes care*. 1998 May 1;21(5):831-5.
9. Virmani A, Ushabala P, Rao PV. Diabetes mortality in a tertiary referral hospital in India. *The Lancet*. 1990 Jun 2;335(8701):1341.
10. Marshall WA, Tanner JM. Variations in pattern of pubertal changes in girls. *Arch Dis Child*. 1969; 44:291-303.
11. Marshall WA, Tanner JM. Variations in the pattern of pubertal changes in boys. *Arch Dis Child*. 1970; 45:13-23.
12. Barbosa N, Sanchez CE, Vera JA, Perez W, Thalabard JC, Rieu M. A physical activity questionnaire: Reproducibility and validity. *J Sports Sci Med*. 2007; 6:505-18.
13. Khadilkar VV, Khadilkar AV. Revised Indian academy of pediatrics 2015 growth charts for height, weight and body mass index for 5-18-year-old Indian children. *Indian J Endocrinol Metab*. 2015; 19:470-6.
14. Chiplonkar SA. Trends in nutrient intakes of Indian adults: Computerized diet analysis (CDiet) of cross-sectional surveys between 1998 and 2015. *Curr Nutr Food Sci* 2021;17: 423-32.
15. Indian Council of Medical Research. National Institute of Nutrition. Recommended Dietary Allowances and Estimated Average Requirements Nutrient Requirements for Indians-2020: A Report of the Expert Group Indian Council of Medical Research National Institute of Nutrition. New Delhi: Indian Council of Medical Research.
16. Joel A, Holm K, Kastrup KW, Pedersen SA, Michaelsen KF, Scheike T, et al. Free insulin-like growth factor I serum levels in 1430 healthy children and adults, and its diagnostic value in patients suspected of growth hormone deficiency. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 1997;82: 2497-502.
17. Kayiranwa A. Assessment of growth among children with type 1 diabetes mellitus: A cross-sectional study of factors contributing to stunting (Doctoral dissertation, University of Rwanda).
18. Ogle GD, James S, Dabelea D, Pihoker C, Svensson J, Maniam J, Klatman EL, Patterson CC. Global estimates of incidence of type 1 diabetes in children and adolescents: Results from the International Diabetes Federation Atlas. *Diabetes research and clinical practice*. 2022 Jan 1; 183:109083.
19. Bereda G. Difference between Type 1 And 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences*, 2022;5(12): 2375–2379.
20. Arslanian SA, Menon RK, Gierl AP, Heil BV, Foley Jr TP. Insulin therapy increases low plasma growth hormone binding protein in children with new-onset Type 1 diabetes. *Diabetic medicine*. 1993 Nov;10(9):833-8.
21. Debnath S, Mondal N, Sen J. Double burden of malnutrition among adolescents in India.
22. Moran A, Jacobs Jr DR, Steinberger J, Hong CP, Prineas R, Luepker R, Sinaiko AR. Insulin resistance during puberty: results from clamp studies in 357 children. *Diabetes*. 1999 Oct 1;4 8(10):2039-44.
23. Elbalshy M, Haszard J, Smith H, Kuroko S, Galland B, Oliver N, Shah V, de Bock MI, Wheeler BJ. Effect of divergent continuous glucose monitoring technologies on glycaemic control in type 1 diabetes mellitus: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials. *Diabetic Medicine*. 2022 Aug;39(8):e14854.
24. Dunger D, Ahmed L, Ong K. Growth and body composition in type 1 diabetes mellitus. *Hormone research*. 2002 Sep 1;58(Suppl. 1):66-71.
25. Blasetti A, Castorani V, Polidori N, Mascioli I, Chiarelli F, Giannini C. Role of glucose variability on linear growth in children with type 1 diabetes. *Endocrine Connections*. 2023 Apr 1;12(4).
26. Kanumakala S, Dabadghao P, Carlin JB, Vidmar S, Cameron FJ. Linear growth and height outcomes in children with early onset type 1 diabetes mellitus—a 10-yr longitudinal study. *Pediatric Diabetes*. 2002 Dec;3(4):189-93.

27. Aljuhani FM, Al-Agha AE, Almunami BA, Meftah EA, Sultan RA, Sultan RA, Alsawadi HM, Alahmadi MM, Albogmi RA, Khaldi SJ. Growth status of children and adolescents with type 1 diabetes mellitus in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia: a cross-sectional study. *Curr Pediatr Res.* 2018;22(3):249-54.